

D3.1 Intermediate Impact Report v0.1

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6GSMART-ICC

Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D

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Dissemination Level	
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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium
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PR	Prototype
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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
5GC	5G Core
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARI	Atos Research and Innovation
B5G	Beyond 5G
CSP	Communication Service Provider
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GR	Group Report
GS	Group Specification
GSMA	Global Standard Mobile Association
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MWC	Mobile World Congress
PPP	Public Private Partnership

PRTR	Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
OSM	Open Source MANO
OT	Operational Technology
OTT	Over-The-Top
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
TJV	Temporary Joint Venture
TM Forum	Tele Management Forum
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URSP	UE Route Selection Policy
ZSM	Zero-touch network and Service Management

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *P1-D3.1 Immediate Impact Report*. It captures the output of tasks T3.1 and T3.2 of the project 6GSMART-ICC (TSI-063000-2021-9), describing the intermediate outputs in terms of scientific dissemination, standardization, and communication activities envisaged in the framework of the project 6GSMART-ICC. Such activities are plan of the strategy to effectively communicating project outcomes, disseminating project results, and engaging relevant stakeholders in standardisation efforts. This deliverable is closely related to the activities of the project and provides a structured approach to ensure successful dissemination, communication, and standardisation throughout the project's lifecycle. This document outlines the specific objectives, methodologies, and impact indicators that will be employed to assess the effectiveness of the project's dissemination, communication, and standardisation efforts. In this sense, clear guidelines, and best practices for engaging with stakeholders, selecting appropriate communication channels, developing compelling content, and actively monitoring relevant standardisation activities are provided. By following the devised plan, the 6GSMART-ICC project aims to establish a strong presence in the scientific community, industry, and standardisation organisations. Moreover, this document presents an intermediate impact report, providing a summary of the efforts and KPIs achieved so far.

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides a plan and intermediate report of the scientific dissemination, standardization, and communication activities of the 6GSMART-ICC project (TSI-063000-2021-9), along with a plan for future activities. This plan plays a crucial role in guiding the project team's efforts to effectively communicate project outcomes, disseminate research results, and engage relevant stakeholders in standardisation efforts. By establishing a comprehensive strategy, this document serves as a roadmap to ensure the successful dissemination, communication, and standardisation of the project's activities and achievements throughout its lifecycle.

The dissemination, communication and standardisation plan is an integral part of the overall project framework, closely intertwined with the project's activities, research objectives, and collaboration with external stakeholders. It provides a structured approach that aligns with the project's goals and ensures that the project's outcomes reach the intended target audiences, including academia, industry, policymakers, and the wider research community.

The plan encompasses a range of strategies and activities oriented to achieve the dissemination of project results, effective communication practices, and active involvement in relevant standardisation initiatives. It aims to maximise the project's visibility, impact, and contribution to the advancement of Smart Industry enabler technologies (specifically, industrial cloud-continuum orchestration and public-private resource integration), both within the project consortium and in the broader scientific and technological community. This deliverable offers valuable insights and recommendations to ensure that the project's outcomes are effectively communicated, valuable collaborations are established, and the project's contributions to standardisation efforts are recognised and integrated into the evolving landscape of 6GSMART-ICC technologies. By following this comprehensive plan, the 6GSMART-ICC project aims to establish a strong presence within the scientific community, industry stakeholders, and standardisation organisations. The project strives to accelerate the adoption of edge computing and cloud native technologies in the Smart Industry domain through effective dissemination, communication, and active engagement in standardisation.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

The scope of *P1-D3.1 Immediate Impact Report* is two-fold. First, it aims to outline the strategies, activities, and objectives related to disseminating project outcomes, engaging with stakeholders, and ensuring compliance with relevant standardisation processes. This document provides guidance and direction for the project team to effectively communicate project results, engage with target audiences. Second, it provides a report

on the achievements of the project so far in terms of scientific dissemination, standardization, and communication activities.

This document aims to encompass information on planned and achieved dissemination, communication, and promotion activities and KPIs, including standardisation efforts for the project. It outlines the project's strategy for dissemination and communication and provides an action plan to guide these activities throughout the project's duration. The strategy includes specific and measurable impact indicators, such as the number of scientific publications, frequency of web posts, targeted standardisation forums, and a list of strategic events for project showcase.

Such activities are planned to generate beneficial tools for the project execution in terms of visibility, outreach, and feedback. The planned activities are detailed and encompass webpage creation and maintenance, regular activity in social media channels to promote the project, scientific dissemination through peer-reviewed publications and conference workshops/presentations, and identification of specific standardisation fora and bodies to follow and potentially contribute to. Quantifiable impact indicators are defined to measure the level of accomplishment throughout the project.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable is framed within the Work Package 3 of the SMART-ICC project. This Work Package is responsible for promoting the dissemination of project results in scientific and industrial fora, engaging stakeholders and research communities. It also emphasises the alignment with relevant standardisation activities and bodies, as well as open-source communities. Additionally, it focuses on defining an exploitation strategy to analyse market intentions and ensuring alignment with the roadmap of relevant bodies such as 5G-ACIA.

This deliverable is the joint result of tasks T3.1 and T3.2, which are outlined below:

- T3.1 Communication and Outreach: this task is a coordinated action across all 6GSMART subprojects and it aims to ensure that the project outcomes are accessible to the broadest target audiences. Activities include, but are not limited to:
 - Development of the project webpage and generation of content in social media accounts.
 - Monitoring and engagement with other research projects of the 5G/6G ecosystem.
- T3.2 Dissemination and Standardization: This task focuses on ensuring the project impact in the scientific and industrial communities in the OT and IT fields. In particular, activities in this task include:
 - Publishing the project's proposals and results at high impact peer-reviewed journals and magazines and presenting in renowned international conferences and workshops.

- Promotion of project developments of interest to Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) and Industrial Associations, such as 3GPP, IEEE, 5G-ACIA, and ETSI.

Furthermore, this deliverable directly aligns with the core objectives of Work Package 3 of the 6GSMART-ICC project. The aforementioned objectives can be summarised as:

- Perform communication and outreach activities to guarantee that the project outcomes reach the public.
- Maximise the impact of the project through dissemination in scientific conferences and journals.
- Exploit project results by means of IPR generation, identification of licensing opportunities and creating synergistic collaborations among partners in Horizon Europe activities.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides an overview of the project's dissemination activities.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the project's standardisation activities.
- Section 4 provides an overview of the project's communication and outreach activities.
- Section 5 provides impact indicators.
- Concludes the document.

2 Communication and Outreach Activities

Communication and outreach activities aim to support and maximise the 6GSMART-ICC project impact, by raising awareness and ensuring maximum visibility of project results and progress among stakeholders and key audiences. The specific objectives of the communication and outreach activities presented in this document are as follows:

- To raise awareness about the 6GSMART-ICC project among relevant stakeholders, including academia, industry, policymakers, and the general public.
- To engage with relevant stakeholder groups, tailoring the messaging and content to their specific needs and interests and establishing a distinctive identity to support promotional purposes.
- To effectively promote the project's activities and achievements by using various communication tools and platforms, including websites, social media, and events.
- To facilitate information sharing, collaboration, and coordination among team members by establishing clear and consistent internal communication channels within the project consortium.

The first phase of the plan aimed to raising awareness about the project, identifying key stakeholder communities and target audiences. As such, the plan is intended follow the evolution of the project, and to raise awareness and ensure maximum visibility of project's motivation, results, and progress among stakeholders and key audiences. The progress will be communicated through various channels and activities until reaching a phase where the main aim is to promote results and uptake by external communities.

From a communication point of view, the focus is to ensure that relevant stakeholders such as research communities and organisations involved in activities and topics relevant to 6GSMART-ICC are aware of the project's existence, motivation, expected outcomes, and how those results can benefit them according to their roles.

2.1 Communication Plan

To build a strong impact strategy, communication activities must be considered complementary to dissemination and standardization efforts. Considering the duration of the project, the planned technical progress and the main milestones, and the intertwining between communication, dissemination and standardisation efforts, the following phases are defined:

1. Awareness creation: this phase intends to design the communication strategy and plan, including identification of key stakeholder communities and target audiences with whom the project can begin to establish relationships. It also aims to identify relevant projects and initiatives, to find common practices, synergies, and opportunities for collaboration in community-building activities. From a communication point of view, the focus is on ensuring that people and organisations involved in activities and topics relevant for 6GSMART-ICC are

aware of the project's existence, motivation, expected outcomes, and how those results can benefit them according to their roles. Moreover, introducing the partners involved in the project and the scenarios where the technologies developed will be validated constitutes another valuable topic to share with external audiences.

2. Community outreach: this phase is intended to demonstrate the progress and to engage with relevant stakeholders to collect valuable feedback considering their various points of view.
3. Global outreach and sustainable impact: the objective of this phase is to actively engage and support the uptake and deployment of the concepts, technologies and tools offered by 6GSMART-ICC through dedicated promotional activities and materials, publicity of validation activities, further scientific publications, participation in selected events, organisation of planned workshops and exploitation activities with the aim to demonstrate to potential adopters the relevance of the project's technologies and benefits.

2.2 Activities performed by i2CAT

The main communication activities performed by i2CAT involve the creation of project materials, and the establishment of communication channels and tools. These activities are explained in more detail in the following.

2.2.1 Project materials

The definition and generation of the brand and visual elements of 6GSMART-ICC has a significant impact on the execution of various activities, as the goal is to share a consistent and coherent image of the project regardless of the activity, venue, partner participating, etc.

To create a visual identity for the project, report and presentation templates, and videos are used to enhance the dissemination efforts and effectively communicate the project's objectives, key findings, and achievements to different target audiences:

- Report templates: to establish a common visual model to deliver technical reports and deliverables about the project developments, highlighting main novelties in relation to the state-of-the-art.
- Presentation templates: to establish a common visual model to deliver engaging and informative presentations about the project overview, highlighting main novelties in relation to the state-of-the-art.
- Videos: for conveying information in an appealing and accessible manner. The project may utilise videos to showcase demonstrations, explain technical concepts, or present project highlights. Videos can be shared on the project website, social media platforms, or included in presentations and demos to captivate the audience and increase the visibility and understanding of the project's work.

This visual identity is applied consistently across all communication materials, including the deliverables, presentations, and promotional items. The visual identity not only creates a cohesive and appealing visual experience but also contributes to the overall success of the project's communication and dissemination efforts. The following visual identity guidelines are followed in the project:

1. All publications, communications, and websites associated with the project shall indicate the funding entities, namely the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGenerationEU. This acknowledgment will be in line with the "framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (PRTR)" as specified in article 34.2 of the "Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council".
2. The visual identity of the project shall be maintained by displaying the UE banner with the statement "funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU" in all communication activities. Additionally, the logo of the PRTR will be incorporated appropriately. These elements shall be included in various communication materials, including posters, electronic publications, and the project website.
3. The project is committed to promoting gender equality, inclusivity, and diversity in all communication activities. Images that discriminate against women will be avoided, and communication materials will aim to represent a diverse range of roles and perspectives. It is essential to refrain from using sexist language in all project-related communication activities.

By respecting the established visual identity guidelines, the 6GSMART-ICC project ensures a consistent and coherent representation across all communication channels and materials. This approach not only highlights the project's funding sources but also promotes gender equality, diversity, and inclusivity throughout its communication activities.

2.2.1.1 Document Templates

In order to maintain a consistent and professional visual identity for the 6GSMART-ICC project, a comprehensive set of document templates has been created. These templates serve as standardised formats for presentations, deliverables, and other project reports. The availability of these templates ensures that all project members and subcontractors can create materials that adhere to the established visual identity guidelines.

The document templates have been thoughtfully designed to showcase the project's key information and results in a visually appealing and cohesive manner. They incorporate the funding logos, project's identifier and other relevant visual elements. By utilising these standardised templates, project members can easily create high-quality documents that maintain a consistent look and feel across all project deliverables. In this way, the 6GSMART-ICC project can effectively communicate its progress, findings, and achievements in a visually appealing and coherent manner.

An example of the project's deliverable template can be seen in Figure 1. This template provides a structured layout with predefined sections for the document's objectives,

scope, structure, and conclusions. It also includes placeholders for tables, figures, and acronyms to effectively illustrate and support the presented information.

Access to these document templates is granted to all project members and subcontractors, ensuring that everyone involved in the project can produce materials that align with the established visual identity. These templates are made available through the project's Sharepoint space, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: 6GSMART-ICC deliverable template.

Figure 2: Deliverable template available on 6GSMART-ICC Sharepoint space.

2.2.2 Communication Tools

This section outlines the various tools and platforms that will be leveraged to reach the target audience through digital channels. By employing a diverse array of communication tools, the project aims to maximise its outreach, enhance knowledge sharing, and foster collaboration within the relevant communities.

2.2.2.1 Project Website

The project website plays a crucial role in facilitating dissemination and communication activities. With a focus on providing a seamless user experience, a common website for the UNICO I+D 6G program¹ coordinated by i2CAT has been developed to cater for both desktop and mobile users, following responsive design principles. Moreover, the website adheres to the Visual Identity requirements established by the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience from the Spanish Government². This space, depicted in Figure 3, provides key information about the program and summarises the different projects framed within this initiative. Visitors can access detailed information about the program's activities and updates, both past and upcoming. Additionally, the site serves as a centralised repository for ongoing tendering calls.

On the aforementioned website, a dedicated subsite has been integrated specifically for the 6GSMART coordinated project³. This subsite offers a comprehensive overview of the project, including its main objectives and a brief introduction to each one of the sub-projects, including 6GSMART-ICC, as illustrated in Figure 4. Acting as a dedicated space for dissemination and communication, the website will provide access to a wide range of materials, including technical specifications, reports, blogs, videos, and news about events and activities such as conferences and exhibitions. It will serve as the primary source of information regarding the project's activities, developments, and results and

¹ <https://i2cat.net/unico/>

² <https://planderecuperacion.gob.es/identidad-visual>

³ <https://i2cat.net/unico/6gsmart/>

will be the primary platform for sharing projects results and updates with the general audience.

Figure 3: Website for the UNICO I+D 6G program coordinated by i2CAT.

Figure 4: 6GSMART subsite.

To effectively disseminate the project's achievements, the 6GSMART subsite includes a dedicated "News" section. This section will provide regular updates on the project's progress, milestones, and notable accomplishments. It serves as a valuable resource for visitors to stay informed about the latest developments and milestones.

Furthermore, the website incorporates a "Documents" section providing access to open-access scientific publications related to the project, including journals, conferences, workshops, and other relevant sources. To enhance the user experience and provide further relevant information, the subsite includes links to other relevant sites, such as blog posts from the project, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration.

In order to ensure the long-term accessibility of project results, the UNICO I+D 6G program website, which hosts the 6GSMART subsite, will remain active for a minimum of two years after the conclusion of the project. This guarantees the sustained availability of valuable project information and resources.

Overall, the 6GSMART subsite serves as a comprehensive platform for disseminating project updates, sharing research findings, and providing access to valuable resources, fostering engagement and knowledge exchange with the project's target audience. It plays a crucial role in communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring effective engagement with the general audience and facilitating knowledge dissemination within the 6GSMART-ICC project.

2.2.2.2 Social Media

The 6GSMART-ICC project recognises the significance of social media platforms, which play a crucial role in facilitating communication, dissemination, and engagement with stakeholders. Therefore, the project actively maintains a presence on social media, leveraging these platforms to disseminate news, events, and achievements. Specifically, i2CAT's Twitter⁴ and LinkedIn⁵ accounts serve as key channels for sharing project updates and news, ensuring that the latest developments are communicated effectively to a wide audience. Leveraging these social media accounts, the project aims to reach a wide and diverse audience by conducting targeted campaigns centred around project news, events, and achievements.

The project acknowledges the unique audience offered by the Twitter platform, particularly when combined with the use of hashtags. Figure 5 provides an example of previous communication efforts carried out by i2CAT via its X (formerly Twitter) account, specifically promoting a 6GSMART workshop held back in October 2023.

⁴ <https://twitter.com/i2CAT>

⁵ <https://es.linkedin.com/company/i2cat-foundation>

Figure 5: 6GSMART workshop post on i2CAT's X account.

Similarly, the 6GSMART-ICC project has extended its reach to the i2CAT LinkedIn account, recognising it as a preferred platform for researchers, companies, and industry professionals. LinkedIn plays a significant role in facilitating communication and sharing news, events, and outcomes related to the project. By utilising the project consortium's individual pages on LinkedIn, posts can be easily shared, amplifying the impact and reach of dissemination and communication activities. Figure 4-4 provides an example of previous communication efforts carried out by i2CAT via its LinkedIn account, specifically showcasing communication related to the publication of a project blogpost.

Figure 6: 6GSMART-ICC post on i2CAT's LinkedIn account.

By leveraging these platforms, the project can effectively share updates, highlight milestones, and engage with the public, industry professionals, and other relevant communities. These examples serve as valuable references, demonstrating effective utilisation of social media platforms to disseminate project information, attract stakeholders, and foster collaboration.

To ensure comprehensive coverage, the i2CAT Corporate Development department works closely with the project's research team. This collaboration aims to keep track of the project's progress, identify significant achievements, and develop communication content that can attract media attention. Communication content is carefully crafted to highlight the project's innovations, advancements, and their potential impact on the field. i2CAT also integrates information about the 6GSMART-ICC project into external campaigns that focus on disseminating the center's broader research strategy in the domains of 5G and 6G.

Through a combination of social media posts and news on the website, the 6GSMART-ICC project aims to extend its reach beyond the project's immediate stakeholders. By effectively utilising social media platforms and engaging with the media, the project can

maximise its visibility, create awareness about its objectives, and foster collaboration and knowledge exchange within the wider community.

2.2.2.3 Internal Communication

The internal communication plays a crucial role in facilitating effective collaboration, coordination, and knowledge sharing among the partners of the 6GSMART-ICC project. A structured approach is followed to ensure effective communication and coordination among its participants. The various tools, platforms, and practices employed to foster seamless communication within the project team are outlined next.

Meetings serve as a fundamental means to facilitate effective communication and collaboration among project partners, allowing team members to gather, discuss progress, exchange ideas, and address any challenges. Regular project meetings are scheduled to ensure that all team members are updated on the project's status, milestones, and deliverables. These meetings provide an opportunity for open dialogue, brainstorming, and decision-making.

Specifically, the project schedule includes a monthly meeting that includes at least one representative per participant organisation. These meetings cover both managerial and technical aspects, overseeing the project progress, and enabling decision making, commitments, and next steps. Additional ad-hoc meetings are arranged on demand to address specific issues or to facilitate focused discussions between relevant partners.

To facilitate seamless communication and collaboration, the project leverages dedicated platforms such as project management and collaboration systems for document sharing (i.e., Sharepoint), virtual meetings software (i.e., Google Meet) and messaging tools (i.e., Gmail and Slack). These platforms enable team members to share project-related documentation, track progress, assign tasks, and collaborate on shared files in a centralised and organised manner. By utilising such platforms, the project team has real-time access to project-related information, enabling collaborative work in an efficient manner. In summary, the platforms employed to streamline internal communication and document sharing among the team involved in 6GSMART-ICC include Sharepoint, Google Meet, Slack and Gmail.

Documentation plays a critical role in the internal communication by providing a comprehensive, updated and easily accessible repository of project-related information. Documentation includes technical documents, progress reports, meeting slides, and so forth. The project team has access to these documents to ensure transparency, facilitate knowledge transfer, and ensure consistency in the understanding project objectives and requirements. In order to enforce a consistent format, document templates are used for the delivery of project documentation (as presented in Section 2.2.1.1).

By implementing robust internal communication guidelines, the 6GSMART-ICC project aims to foster a collaborative and cohesive environment where team members can effectively communicate, share knowledge, and work towards achieving project objectives. Established mechanisms and practices underscore the project's commitment

to seamless internal communication, ensuring all team members are aligned, informed, and actively engaged in the project's progress.

2.2.3 Initial Outputs

Relevant communication actions performed include:

- Two internal UNICO I+D workshops held at i2CAT in December 2022 and June 2023, respectively, which served as a platform to discuss project development strategy.
- A 6GSMART workshop held at i2CAT on the 5th of October 2023. This served as an encounter point for project partners to discuss in person the technical details of the project's use cases and the integration plan in scope of the technologies developed in the project.
- i2CAT's UNICO I+D strategy presentation at the V5gValencia in November 2023, with a specific mention to the 6GSMART project.

As of the 23rd of November, 2023, a subset of relevant social media impact metrics were as follows:

- Social media posts about UNICO I+D June 2023 workshop held at i2CAT
 - X: 560 post impressions, 86 interactions.
 - LinkedIn: 558 reproductions.
- Social media posts about 6GSMART October 2023 workshop held at i2CAT
 - X: 717 post impressions, 123 interactions.
 - LinkedIn: 715 reproductions.
- Social media posts about i2CAT's UNICO I+D strategy presentation at the V5gValencia in November 2023
 - X: 207 post impressions, 6 interactions.
 - LinkedIn: 202 reproductions.
- Social media posts about 6GSMART-ICC blogpost publication in November 2023
 - X: 374 impressions, 17 interactions.
 - LinkedIn: 367 reproductions.

3 Dissemination Activities

Dissemination activities are of utmost importance to support and maximise the 6GSMART-ICC project impact. Therefore, the impact creation strategy aims to raise awareness and ensure maximum visibility of project results and progress among stakeholders and key audiences. Dissemination tactics and activities are mainly focused on publication of scientific papers at journals and conferences. The specific objectives of the dissemination activities are as follows:

- To make the project's findings, insights, and outcomes available in order to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field of industrial edge orchestration and industrial private-public integration models.
- To reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of stakeholders from the various target areas to ensure that the results of 6GSMART-ICC are effectively showcased, leading to validation, improvement and possibly wider adoption of the technologies and concepts developed.
- To maximise the visibility and impact of the project by effectively disseminating research findings, technical advancements, and innovative solutions through various channels and platforms.
- To engage and collaborate with relevant research, innovation and policy making initiatives, liaising with related projects and working groups within 3GPP, IEEE, 5G-ACIA, ETSI, or other relevant bodies.

The first phase of the dissemination plan was devoted to raising awareness about the project, identifying key stakeholder communities and target audiences. Then, for the second phase, the availability of partial results is fundamental to demonstrate the progress and engage with stakeholders targeted in the first phase, thus supporting business cases and exploitation tasks promoting the final results.

3.1 Activities performed by i2CAT

To guarantee the accuracy and integrity of the research outcomes, and to enhance their impact and outreach, a standard publication procedure has been proposed. In addition, ongoing work is trying to identify projects to establish potential collaborations with.

3.1.1 Publication Procedure and Acknowledgements

To guarantee the accuracy and integrity of the research outcomes, a standardised publication procedure is proposed. Its aim is to establish clear guidelines for publications,

including the review process, authorship, and acknowledgements, while ensuring proper recognition of funding sources, project partners, and contributors in all publications.

Within this procedure, the main author is responsible for circulating the final draft of the publication to the co-authors for review. This step ensures that all co-authors have an opportunity to provide input, suggest revisions, and verify the accuracy of the content. The feedback received from the co-authors will be incorporated into the final version of the manuscript. The authors will be established according to the contribution to the paper writing and the technical/scientific work behind. Furthermore, where possible cross-organisation authorship will be fostered to maximise the impact of the publication including multiple business corners and technical perspectives.

Once the final draft has been approved by all co-authors, the manuscript will be submitted to appropriate venues for further evaluation through the peer-review process. This process involves subjecting the publication to the scrutiny of independent experts in the relevant field who assess the scientific rigor, validity, and novelty of the research. Upon acceptance of the publication, it will be made available on the project's website, ensuring open access for interested parties. By sharing the publications on the website, the project aims to disseminate the knowledge and findings to a wide audience, including researchers and industry professionals.

As part of the publication procedure, it is crucial to acknowledge the contributions and support received throughout the project. Therefore, all publications, conference proceedings, presentations at workshops, seminars, or public events related to the 6GSMART-ICC project must include the following acknowledgment text. This acknowledgment ensures proper recognition and attribution to the funding entities and stakeholders involved in the project:

“This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGenerationEU, in the framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (PRTR) (Call UNICO I+D 5G 2021, ref. number TSI-063000-2021-9-6GSMART-ICC).”

By adhering to a systematic publication procedure and acknowledging the project's funding sources, the 6GSMART-ICC project ensures the quality, transparency, and accountability of its research publications.

3.1.2 Collaborations with other Projects

To enhance the impact and reach of the achieved results in the 6GSMART-ICC project, collaborations with other EU-funded projects will be sought. By joining forces with these projects, the dissemination of conducted work will be strengthened, and its significance will be amplified.

As part of the initial assessment, the following EU project has been identified as potential candidate for collaboration. This project shares common objectives, partners and areas of interest with 6GSMART-ICC, making it an ideal target to establish a collaboration with:

Zero-enabling smart networked control framework for agile cyber physical production systems of systems (Zero-SWARM), is a Horizon Europe project with a total public private investment of almost €10 million launched on the 1st June 2022, aiming to accelerate the uptake of advanced 5G technologies by European manufacturing sector. The project mission is to achieve climate neutral and digitized production via a multidisciplinary, human centric, objective oriented innovative approach resulting in technical solutions for open swarm framework, non-public 5G network, active information continuum and digital twin. In essence, it establishes a unique forum where separately maturing technologies of 5G and cloud-edge continuum, data technologies and analysis (including data spaces and GAIA-X) and operational technology (automation and agility) break their siloes to co-design and co-create through 10 trials.

This project includes i2CAT and Innovalia among its partners. Zero-SWARM's focus on 5G and cloud continuum technologies aligns closely with the objectives of the 6GSMART-ICC project. By collaborating with this and potentially other additional projects, 6GSMART-ICC aims to leverage their expertise, resources, and networks to maximise the impact of the project research outcomes. Through joint dissemination activities, such as joint publications, workshops, conferences, and knowledge sharing initiatives, we can broaden the scope of our audience and engage with a wider community of researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. Furthermore, the inclusion of i2CAT and Innovalia as partners in both 6GSMART and Zero-SWARM, strengthens the potential for collaboration and knowledge exchange. The shared partnership provides a solid foundation for joint activities, such as workshops, conferences, and publications, to disseminate the outcomes of the projects and foster mutual learning.

Moreover, the collaboration with Zero-SWARM will provide valuable opportunities to exchange ideas, share best practices, and foster synergies that can accelerate the adoption and utilisation of 6GSMART-ICC's findings. Through these collaborations, we can collectively contribute to advancing the field of industrial cloud continuum orchestration and its advancement to achieve a cost-effective applicability in practical contexts.

By actively engaging with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, we not only enhance the visibility and impact of our own project but also contribute to the overall advancement of research and innovation in the field. Through fruitful collaborations, we can create a strong ecosystem of knowledge exchange, collaboration, and innovation that benefits the entire Smart Industry community.

3.1.3 Initial Outputs

As a research institution, i2CAT aims to disseminate 6GSMART-ICC results in high impact journal and magazine publications, as well as in high-calibre international conferences. Currently, the following publications are work in progress and planned to be submitted in early 2024:

- One magazine article to be tentatively submitted to the Industrial IoT track of the IEEE IoT Magazine⁶.
- One position paper to be submitted to a journal publication, such as IEEE Access⁷ or Elsevier Computer Networks⁸.
- One conference paper to be submitted to an IEEE ICC workshop⁹, in collaboration with the Zero-SWARM project

⁶ <https://www.comsoc.org/publications/magazines/ieee-internet-things-magazine/cfp/vertical-area-2-industrial-iot>

⁷ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=6287639>

⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computer-networks>

⁹ <https://icc2024.ieee-icc.org/workshop/ws-08-third-workshop-industrial-private-5g-and-bond-wireless-networks>

4 Standardization Activities

Standardisation activities are intended to support and maximise the 6GSMART-ICC project impact, by raising awareness and ensuring maximum visibility of project results and progress among stakeholders and key audiences. Standardization tactics are oriented toward ensuring that the project's outcomes align with existing standards and frameworks and, in turn, enhancing visibility of the EU funding. The concrete objectives of the standardisation plan are as follows:

- To identify relevant standardisation activities and initiatives in the field of industrial edge orchestration and industrial private-public integration models, ensuring the project's alignment with existing standards and frameworks.
- To incorporate standardisation requirements and considerations into the project's research, development, and deployment processes, promoting interoperability, compatibility, and scalability of the developed solutions.
- To contribute to the dissemination of standardisation outputs and promote their adoption within the wider Smart Industry and 5G/6G communities, fostering harmonisation and collaboration across different projects and initiatives.
- To identify opportunities and potentially participate in standardisation organisations, forums, and working groups to share project findings, insights, and recommendations, influencing the development of standards in the field.

4.1 Activities performed by i2CAT

Although i2CAT has not performed any standardisation activities in the scope of the technical developments of the 6GSMART-ICC project, it has however identified the following forums and standardisation bodies of interest to 6G-SMART-ICC, which it actively follows:

- 5G-ACIA¹⁰: This is the central global forum for shaping 5G in the industrial domain, where relevant ICT and OT stakeholders try to shape the Smart Industry ecosystem and set the necessary frameworks for its development. i2CAT monitors 5G-ACIA activities to align its design and development activities in the scope of the industrial cloud continuum orchestration with the relevant industrial frameworks.
- ETSI MEC¹¹: ETSI's Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) offers application developers and content providers cloud-computing capabilities and an IT service environment at the edge of the network. Relevant ETSI MEC standards are monitored and followed by i2CAT in the development of the 6GSMART-ICC orchestration system in the industrial edge.

¹⁰ <https://5g-acia.org>

¹¹ <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/multi-access-edge-computing>

- CAMARA project¹²: i2CAT actively follows the CAMARA project developments to align the design of the 6GSMART-ICC orchestration system with the CAMARA framework to be able to take advantage of relevant APIs.
- 3GPP¹³: i2CAT follows standardisation activities related to the 3GPP CAPIF Framework to align the design of the 6GSMART-ICC orchestration system with it, to enable future development and integrations that can leverage such framework, facilitating the standardisation and integration of the orchestration stack.

¹² <https://camaraproject.org>

¹³ <https://www.3gpp.org/technologies/rnaa>

5 Impact Indicators and Reporting

This section outlines the key impact indicators that will be monitored throughout the project's lifecycle, along with the reporting mechanisms and tools that will be utilised to gather relevant data. By systematically collecting and analysing data, the project can gain valuable insights into the effectiveness of its activities and the extent to which it is meeting its goals. The establishment of clear indicators and the implementation of a robust reporting framework allows the project to track its achievements, evaluate its outcomes, and provide evidence of its impact.

5.1 Impact Indicators

To assess the performance and effectiveness of the dissemination and communication activities of the 6GSMART-ICC project, a set of impact indicators has been established. These Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will provide valuable insights into the reach, engagement, and influence of the project's dissemination and communication efforts to ensure the project's objectives are effectively communicated to target audiences maximising its impact. lists the KPIs defined to measure the impact generation of 6GSMART-ICC.

Type	KPI	Target
Website	Blog and news entries	At least one blogpost per partner organisation
X	Posts mentioning #6GSMART, #UNICO6G or #UNICO	1 post per month
	Re-posts	2 re-posts per month
	Likes	6 likes per month
LinkedIn	Posts mentioning #6GSMART, #UNICO6G and/or #UNICO	1 post per month
	Post impressions	15 impressions per month
	Post reactions	15 reactions per month
Marketing material	Slide presentations	1 slide deck for the project overview
	Brochures	1 set (to cover i2CAT's UNICO programme)
	Videos	1

	Publications in partners' newsletters	2
Scientific dissemination	Scientific publications in conferences	Acknowledgement in 3 conference papers
	Articles in specialised magazines and/or journals	Acknowledgement in 3 journal or magazine articles
Standardisation and pre-standardisation	Number of standards monitored	2
Events	Workshops organised	1
	Attendees to project workshops	20
	Demo events/videos	3 demo videos for the 6GSMART coordinated project
	Events and presentations where the project will be disseminated	2 for the 6GSMART coordinated project
Collaboration	Liaisons and joint activities with other projects, communities, initiatives, etc. (e.g., website links, workshops, newsletters, social media, joint publications, etc.)	3

5.1.1 Reporting

To ensure effective tracking and planning of dissemination and communication activities, the 6GSMART project has implemented a comprehensive event and publication tracking methodology that is applied throughout all subprojects, including 6GSMART-ICC. This methodology enables project members to monitor and report on various aspects related to dissemination and communication efforts. The following key elements are incorporated into the tracking process:

1. Reporting: Project participants can use monthly meetings (for more details, refer to Section 2.2.2.3) to provide an updated report detailing the anticipated dissemination opportunities, planned attendance at events, and publications associated with the project. These reports serve as an updated overview of the ongoing and upcoming activities.
2. Event Information: The reporting includes essential details about events, such as the location, participants, contributions made by the project team, and any other relevant

information. This allows the project to track its presence and contributions in different events accurately.

3. **Audience Analysis:** Project partners are requested to provide information on the number and type of audience reached during events or dissemination activities. This helps in assessing the outreach and impact of the project's communication efforts and enables targeted engagement with specific stakeholder groups.
4. **Future Outcomes and Impact:** The reports also capture the projected outcomes and potential impact resulting from the conducted activities. This includes identifying potential publications, establishing new contacts, and other relevant future outcomes. By tracking these aspects, the project can evaluate the effectiveness and long-term impact of its dissemination and communication initiatives.
5. **Impact Tracking Report:** To keep track of activities performed by partners, an impact tracking report has been created and shared on 6GSMART's repository on Sharepoint. This ensures access to a comprehensive overview of the project's progress, achievements, and impact in terms of dissemination and communication. As an example, Figure 7 shows the impact tracking summary table format, as included in the tracking report on the shared repository on Sharepoint.

	Year 1 Target	Total Target	Listed (to 6GSMART)	Accepted	Pending
Publications: Journals, Articles, ...					
Conferences Proceedings					
5G-CLARITY Workshops					
Whitepapers & Industry Related Publications					
Industrial Event Participations					
5G Initiative Participation					
Standard Contributions					
Open Source Contributions					
Press Releases					
Newsletter					
Social Media Posts					
Patents					

Figure 7: Impact tracking summary table format.

By implementing this event and publication tracking methodology, the 6GSMART-ICC project gains valuable insights into its dissemination and communication efforts. The impact tracking report enables project members to assess the effectiveness of their activities, identify potential areas for improvement, and plan future actions. Furthermore, the integration of these reports into the project's deliverables provides a comprehensive record of the project's dissemination and communication achievements over time. This tracking methodology enhances the project's ability to measure its impact, facilitate collaboration, and ensure the successful delivery of its dissemination and communication objectives.

6 Conclusions

The dissemination, communication and standardisation plan and outputs presented in this document outlines a comprehensive strategy and its efficacy so far to disseminate project outcomes, communicate key messages, engage stakeholders, and ensure alignment with relevant standardisation activities. By aligning the dissemination and communication efforts with the objectives of the 6GSMART-ICC project, we aim to maximise the impact of our research and ensure its relevance in scientific, industrial, and commercial fora.

A coordinated approach is pursued to leverage the expertise of project partners in their respective domains. i2CAT mostly contributes through scientific publications and conference presentations, fostering knowledge exchange within the scientific community. By actively seeking feedback from stakeholders, the project's exploitation potential can be enhanced. This ongoing dialogue allows us to refine our approaches, address challenges, and seize opportunities for further collaboration and impact.

Furthermore, the plan underscores the importance of measurable performance indicators. By defining specific indicators such as the number of scientific publications, frequency of web posts, interactions with relevant fora, and strategic events for project showcase, we can assess the effectiveness of our dissemination and communication efforts. These indicators will help us monitor our progress, identify areas for improvement, and demonstrate the value and impact of the 6GSMART-ICC project.

In conclusion, the Dissemination, Communication and Standardisation Plan presented in this document provides a roadmap for effectively disseminating project outcomes, engaging stakeholders, contributing to standardisation efforts, and ensuring the long-term success of the 6GSMART-ICC project. By following this plan and leveraging the expertise and collaboration of our partners, we are confident in our ability to create significant impact, foster innovation, and drive technological adoption in the Smart Industry.

Regarding KPI achievement, no risks are foreseen. i2CAT is on track to submit 2 conference papers and one journal article at the beginning of 2024. Additional publications are expected in collaboration with the other sub-project partners towards the end of the project, when developments can be demonstrated and showcased. In addition, interactions in social media have been dozens of interactions within a few hours of being published. And last, 6GSMART-ICC has already established a good collaboration link with the H2020 project Zero-SWARM.